

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE FUNDAMENTALS OF DIFFERENTIAL AND INTEGRAL CALCULUS.

Shodiyev Erkin Oltiboyevich¹

shodiyeverkin3@gmail.com

+998(91)577-04-49

Dursoatov Mansur Bozor o'g'li²

dursoatovm@gmail.com

+998(94)904-34-33

Faculty of Information Technologies of
¹⁻²Termez State University 2nd stage students

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7151555>

Abstract: The development and content of integral calculus is inextricably linked with the development and content of differential calculus. This article provides the necessary information about the critical analysis of the fundamentals of differential and integral calculus.

Key words: differential, integral, Newton, Leibniz, "Newton's binomial", Tangent. Integral calculus is a branch of mathematics that studies integrals and their properties, calculation methods, and applications. The development and content of integral calculus is inextricably linked with the development and content of differential calculus. Integral calculus together with differential calculus constitutes the analysis of infinitesimal quantities (see Mathematical analysis). By the 17th century, the development of technology and natural sciences presented many new problems to mathematics, including the problems of calculating the surface, volume, and center of gravity of bodies of complex geometric shapes. It was necessary to create new and powerful mathematical methods instead of the ancient old methods of determining them. In this period, Integral calculation was born. The main concepts of integral h. are concepts of definite and indefinite integral. Due to the great importance of definite integrals corresponding to these indefinite integrals in various applications of integral calculus, they are well studied and tables of calculated values are made.

Newton, Leibniz and the infinitesimals. Even the creators of mathematical analysis could not fully prove the methods they discovered. Both Newton and Leibniz were aware of the lack of logic in their works, and each tried in his own way, if not to eliminate, at least to mitigate this flaw.

So Newton went to the limit and tried to avoid using infinitesimals, but he failed. Nevertheless, his efforts were an inspiration to Koshy. We show how to understand the resulting fraction $0/0$ in the expression $h = 0$

necessary to determine the derivative $f'(x)$ is the function f at the point X . Here we allow ourselves a little anachronism. Newton himself never used the concept

of the derivative of a function and did not use such symbols, but instead used the concept of "vanishing quantity". Thus, the difference $f(x + h) - f(x)$ and the number itself h are vanishing quantities: when they both "vanish" h becomes zero. "The last ratio of vanishing quantities" he called the value of the above fraction when $h = 0$. Clearly, Newton meant the transition to the limit when he spoke of the "last ratio of vanishing quantities" to justify the uncertainty of $0/0$, where the above fraction decreases. $h = 0$. However, he did not give a strict definition of this method. Newton himself was aware of this shortcoming and resorted to physical analogies in explanation: "Perhaps you may object that there is no final ratio of vanishing quantities, because before the quantities vanish this ratio is not final, when the quantities disappears. , no relationship exists. However, based on the same logic, it can be denied that a body that has arrived at a certain point and stopped there does not have a final velocity, because before that its velocity was not final, and after the body has reached this point, its velocity is zero. However, the answer to this question is very simple. Final velocity is defined as the velocity of movement of the body at the time of arrival, neither earlier nor later, that is, the velocity at which the body reached the final point and its motion stopped. In the same way, the last ratio should be understood as the lost ratio of the quantities, neither before nor after their loss. Infinitesimal quantities played a significantly larger role in Leibniz's mathematical analysis. For example, they understood the very definition of the curve used by Leibniz. For Newton, a curve is formed by a point in motion: "I consider mathematical quantities to be described not by very small parts, but by continuous motion. Thus, curves are characterized and created not by the location of parts, but by the continuous movement of points. And Leibniz believed that curves consist of infinitely small line segments: "To find a tangent, one must draw a straight line connecting two points or extended sides of a curve that are at an infinitely small distance. an infinitely many-angled polygon, which for us is equivalent to a curve," Leibniz wrote in 1684.

The concept of a curve is described more clearly in Marquis L'Hôpital's (1696) book Analysis of Infinitesimals. The second postulate of the book is as follows: "We assume that a curve can be thought of as consisting of infinitely many infinitely small lines, or similarly a polygon with an infinite number of sides. of infinitesimal length, and the curvature of the line is determined by the angles between these sides." For a long time, it was believed that this formula, like the triangle, which allows finding coefficients for natural indicators, was invented by Blaise Pascal. But historians of science have discovered that this formula was

known in ancient China in the 13th century, and Islamic mathematicians in the 15th century. Isaac Newton generalized the formula for arbitrary exponents (fractions, negatives, etc.) around 1676. From the binomial expansion, Newton and later Euler derived the entire theory of infinite series.

Newton's Binomial in Literature In fiction, "Newton's binomial" appears in several memorable contexts involving something complex. In A. Conan Doyle's story *Holmes's Last Work*, Holmes says of the mathematician Professor Moriarty: "He wrote a treatise on Newton's binomial at the age of twenty-one, which won him European fame. After that, he took the chair of mathematics in one of our regional universities, and, perhaps, a bright future awaited him." A famous quote from M. A. Bulgakov's *"The Master and Margarita"*: "Think, Newton's binomial!". Later, the same phrase was mentioned in the film *"Stalker"* by A. A. Tarkovsky. Newton's building is mentioned: in Leo Tolstoy's story *"Youth"* in the episode of Nikolai Irteniev's university entrance exams. E. I. Zamyatin. Loyba's origin Leibniz's approach to calculation had its own characteristics. Leibniz thought higher analysis algebraically, not kinematically like Newton. He proceeded to his discovery from the analysis of infinitesimal quantities and the theory of infinite series. In 1675, Leibniz completed his version of mathematical analysis, carefully considered its symbolism and terminology, reflecting the essence of the matter. Almost all of his innovations were rooted in science, and only the term "integral" was introduced by Jacob Bernoulli (1690), Leibniz himself initially called it simply sum.

Derivation Origins As the analysis progressed, it became clear that Leibniz's symbolism, unlike Newton's, was excellent for representing multiple differentiation, partial derivatives, etc. Leibniz's school also benefited from his openness and publicizing of new ideas, which Newton did very reluctantly.

Leibniz's works on mathematics are many and varied. In 1666, he wrote his first essay: "On the Art of Combinatorics." Now, combinatorics and probability theory are compulsory subjects of mathematics in year school. Leibniz invented his own design of adding machine, much better than Pascal's, which could do multiplication, division and extraction of roots. The step roller and moving carriage proposed by him formed the basis of all subsequent adding machines. Leibniz also described the binary number system with the numbers 0 and 1, on which modern computer technology is based.

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